

A detailed project report on the

“Integration of Blockchain and Machine Learning in Banking Sector”

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Submitted By:

**‘Kushagra Dixit’
(U2051018)**

Under the supervision of

**“Dr. Pooja”
(Assistant Professor)**

**Department of Electronics and Communication
Faculty of Science, University of Allahabad
Prayagraj – 211002 (INDIA)**

Department of Electronics and Communication
(JK Institute of Applied Physics and Technology)
University of Allahabad, Prayagraj – 211 002

Declaration

This is to certify that the project work entitled “ *Integration of Blockchain and Machine Learning in Banking Sector*” is a bonafide work carried out by me bearing University Enrolment Number “**U2051018**” a student of B.Tech. (C.S.E.), 5th Semester in the Department of Electronics and Communication, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj (INDIA), under the esteemed supervision of “*Dr. Pooja*”.

I, declare that the work presented here is carried out by me and has not been submitted anywhere else for the award of any degree/certificates.

Signature
(*Kushagra Dixit*)

Work presented in this report has been done under my supervision.

Signature
(*Dr. Pooja*)

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ABSTRACT

The architecture design by integrating the Blockchain and Machine Learning has gained salience in information systems and information technology research. However, there has not been significant work on the comprehensive and sequential applications of Blockchain integrated Machine Learning in Banking Sector for data validation, data storage, data security and data privacy. We aim to bridge this gap in the literature and discuss how the integration of blockchain and Machine Learning can improve backward and forward linkages in Banking Sector, Machine learning tools allow banks to transform their data streams into actionable insights. The study considers use cases of bank details, transactions and other personal data to demonstrate the application of Machine Learning in data collection, fraud detection, onboarding and data processing and blockchain technology for data validation, data storage, data security, and data transmission. *SHA256* algorithm for encrypting data in the blockchain and *salting* the encrypted data are utilized to make Banking systems decentralized, efficient, fault tolerant, and interoperable. The technology coupling in banking sector can create externalities such as shared benefits, improved coordination between value chain actors, and real-time decision-making for optimal resource allocation and their sustainable utilization in Banking.

Keywords: Blockchain, Machine learning (ML), Artificial Intelligence (AI), SHA256, Decentralized Finance System (De-Fi), Peer to Peer Network (P2P).

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Chapter-1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction to Project: -

Machine Learning technology is one of the most trending technologies with amazing capabilities, whereas Blockchain is the heart of all cryptocurrencies. Blockchain technology is becoming popular day-by-day, as this allows any user to directly deal with others through a highly secure decentralized system without requiring any intermediary. Machine Learning can be applied with Blockchain technology to make it more efficient and better. We will see how machine learning and Blockchain can be combined to get maximum results in this topic. Before starting, let's first understand the basics of both technologies.

- **Blockchain: -**

The idea of Blockchain was proposed by *Stuart Harber* and *W. Scott Stometta* in a research paper in 1991 i.e. 'How to Digitally Timestamp a Document'. The Blockchain technology is *Decentralized* in nature i.e. the admin has not the sole authority of the data, the data is shared with everyone (Peer to Peer network) and it is difficult to change or modify the data in the chain. The data stored in single unit called the Block and the combination of such several blocks are called Blockchain. Every time a data is stored in a block, a unique code is generated known as *Hash* and the same code is saved in the next block known as *Previous Hash*.

(Source: YouTube "Blockchain by Apna College")

If the data is modified or tried to tamper, the *Hash* will be changed automatically and an error will occur because the Hash of one block

will not match with the Previous Hash of the next block, hence, the error will continue and the admins will get to know that the hacker has tried to tamper the data and in which block the data was changed. Thus, this makes Blockchain system more secure, easy to track and makes it very difficult to tamper the data.

(Source: YouTube "Blockchain by Apna College)

Along with that the data which is being stored in the block is initially encrypted using the *SHA256* algorithm (which has 64 hexadecimal characters of 4 bits, so, in total 64×4 bits = 256 bits) into a hexadecimal form to make it more secure.

Hashing Algorithm: -

This has 64 hexadecimal characters.
Each character is of 4 bits.
So in total it has 64×4 bits i.e. 256 bits.

(Source: YouTube "Blockchain by Code Eaters")

Along with *SHA256* encryption another method is used to make the data more secure and un-hackable i.e. *Salting*. Salting is a concept that typically pertains to password hashing. Essentially, it's a unique value that can be added to the end of the password to create a different hash value. This adds a layer of security to the hashing process, specifically against brute force attacks.

- **Machine Learning: -**

Machine learning can be understood as a technology that learns from past data and improves performance with new data. Machine learning is an application of AI that enables systems to learn and improve from experience without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning focuses on developing computer programs that can access data and use it to learn for themselves.

Like how the human brain gains knowledge and understanding, machine learning relies on input, such as training data or knowledge graphs, to understand entities, domains and the connections between them. With entities defined, deep learning can begin.

(Source: exadel.com)

The machine learning process begins with observations or data, such as examples, direct experience or instruction. It looks for patterns in data so it can later make inferences based on the examples provided. The primary aim of ML is to allow computers to learn autonomously without human intervention or assistance and adjust actions accordingly.

• **Integration of Blockchain and ML: -**

Combining Machine Learning and Blockchain together can generate enormous benefits for various industries. Below are some popular benefits of combining Blockchain and Machine Learning for the Organization: -

- i) Enhancing Security
- ii) Surveillance System
- iii) Enhanced Customer Service
- iv) Managing Data
- v) Implementing Trustable Real-Time Transaction Process

(Source: exadel.com)

1.2 Objectives: -

The main objective is to propose an integrated system of Blockchain and Machine Learning in the Banking sector which will make the whole system very much secure, reliable and interactive.

1.3 Literature Survey: -

The idea of combining the two new age technologies i.e. Machine Learning and Blockchain has gained salience in past few years. Many of the research papers and projects have been proposed with a vision of integrating both the technologies and using in a manner that both of the technologies are complementing each other. The idea of Blockchain was also proposed in a research paper in 1991 by *Stuart Harber* and *W. Scott Stometta* titled 'How to Digitally Timestamp a Document'.

In 1957 American mathematician and researcher in Artificial Intelligence *Ray Solomonoff* published a research paper "An Inductive Inference Machine". *IRE Convention Record, Section on Information Theory, Part 2 (1957) 56-62*. This was the first paper written on machine learning. It emphasized the importance of training sequences, and the use of parts of previous solutions to problems in constructing trial solutions to new problems. Solomonoff presented an early version of this paper at the 1956 Dartmouth Summer Research Conference on Artificial Intelligence. After that many more such research papers were published with the vision of uniting both of the technologies: -

- “*An efficient parallel machine learning-based blockchain framework*” by Korean scientists: Chun-Wei Tsai, Yi-Ping Chen, Tzu- Chieh Tang and Yu-Chen Luo in September 2021.
- “*Blockchain technology in supply chain management: insights from machine learning algorithms*” by Japanese scientists: Enna Hirata and Daisuke Watanabe with a Greek scientist Maria Lambrou in December 2020.
- “*Leveraging Blockchain for retraining deep learning architecture in patient-specific arrhythmia classification*” by American scientists: Amit Juneja and Michael Marefat in 2018.
- “*Great partners: how deep learning and blockchain help improve*

business operations together” by Chinese scientists: Suyuan Luo and Tsan-Ming Choi in 2021.

- “*Machine learning in/for blockchain: Future and challenges*” by Fang Chen, Hong Wan, Hua Cai, Guang Cheng in 2021.
- “*P2TIF: A Blockchain and Deep Learning Framework for Privacy-Preserved Threat Intelligence in Industrial IoT*” by Indian Scientists: Prabhat Kumar, Randhir Kumar, Govind P. Gupta, Rakesh Tripathi, Gautam Srivastava September 2022.
- “*BinDaaS: Blockchain-Based Deep-Learning as-a-Service in Healthcare 4.0 Applications*” by Pronaya Bhattacharya; Sudeep Tanwar; Umesh Bodkhe; Sudhanshu Tyagi; Neeraj Kumar.

Chapter-2: Analysis

2.1 Existing System: -

In the current scenario, the banking sector rely on a Centralized System in which every Client (system) is connected to a common server. Hence, all the information is stored in that common server.

(Source: YouTube "Blockchain by Code Eaters")

This server handles all the devices connected with it in a common area network due to which it stores all the information of the clients and manages all the transactions taking place in the banks and makes a proper ledger of it. Thus, responsible for the seamless working of our banking sector.

2.2 Draw back of the Existing System: -

Since, everything has its pros and cons, thus, centralized systems also have its boons and bane. A centralized network architecture is built around a single server that handles all the major processing. Less powerful workstations connect to the server and submit their requests to the central server rather than performing them directly. This can include applications, data storage, and utilities because of which all the information stored is at a single server.

On the other side, the servers are prone to cyber-attacks and hacking. If a hacker attacks the current server and is able to break into it, it will have the full access of all the information stored and the transaction details of the customers. Along with that the present banking system is not very personalized.

2.3 Proposed System: -

In order to make the banking system more secure, personalized and customer friendly, Blockchain and Machine Learning can be integrated in it. Blockchain is a decentralized system and works as a Peer-to-Peer network where many systems are interlinked with each other who work as a single entity.

Distributed P2P Network: -

(Source: YouTube "Blockchain by Code Eaters")

Blockchain follows this law of P2P network hence the copy of the blockchain is available with every Peer which are in connection with each other. If someone tries to alter the data or hack the blockchain, the other members in the network will get to know about the hacking or the data tampering in the particular block.

Similarly, it is required to make our banking system decentralized with the help of Blockchain and the access of the Blockchain will be with the Bank Branch, Zonal Head Office, State Head Office, The Bank Head Office and Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

Storing the data in a blockchain requires various steps, initially in order to store data in the blockchain, the admin (miner) has to solve a mathematical problem to create a new block after which the other members of the group validate and verify the data. After getting the majority, then a new block is rooted.

Blockchain Mining: -

(Source: YouTube "Blockchain by Code Eaters")

After a new block is mined, then we can store the data manually. In order to make the data safe from hackers *SHA256* algorithm is used for encryption which converts the data into 64 hexa-decimal for making it almost impossible for hacking.

Apart from using *SHA256* algorithm, another method is used to the encrypted data more secure i.e. *Salting* where some meaningless characters are salted in the encrypted data which bluffs the hacker and even if the data is decrypted by the hacker, the data would be meaningless.

In order to change anything in the blockchain, one has to raise a request and after majority of the members have accepted the request; then alteration can be made in the blockchain. If somebody tries to alter the data in the blockchain, then every member of the group will get to know about the data tampering from one end, thus, making Blockchain much more secure from external threats.

Machine Learning will be very much beneficial in order of detecting the cyber-attacks.

Everyone is talking about the *Metaverse!* This is hyper-connected virtual ‘world’ of interactions and transactions will have a profound impact on the fintech industry. The new frontier of cryptocurrency, digital tokens, and NFTs, is restructuring online finance. The metaverse gives birth to a host of exciting opportunities, including:

- **Collaborative engagement with customers.** Interactions with and between clients becomes almost synonymous with real-life, though much smoother, and much more secure. For example, customers can attend an investor event, participate in a bank-sponsored program, or work out retirement investment plans with an avatar advisor.
- **New products and markets.** The metaverse economy is a new source of growth and opportunities for banks to insure and lend against virtual real estate, NFTs, and cryptocurrencies. People will continue spending money to own digital assets and spend virtual money in the real world. Banks will be able to make customer interactions such as real sponsorships for virtual events or branch storefronts. You could even enter your PIN to get money in your virtual wallet, walk out of an appointment with your avatar advisor to an ATM or buy a handbag after examining it and ‘trying it out’ virtually. The possibilities are endless and mind-boggling!

Customers today expect 24/7 communication with business and rapid responses. AI- powered interactions with financial institutions can meet such expectations. With the help of data analytics, ML chatbots can create natural interactive experiences with real-time problem-solving and a high level of personalization.

Banks are constantly expanding their use of ML to enhance customer experience and back-office operations. Machine learning tools allow banks to transform their data streams into actionable insights, from operations to business development and marketing.

Usually, businesses turn to machine learning use cases in fintech for faster support, more robust security, and smooth, sleek processes. This section will illustrate the most popular machine learning use cases in banking.

(Source: exadel.com)

Onboarding and Document Processing: -

Machine learning in banking goes far beyond fraud detection and transaction processing. Document processing is traditionally a labor-intensive process requiring effort and time. Machine learning can ultimately reduce time spent organizing, classifying, labeling and processing documents. First, you need to run copies through the Optical Character Recognition (OCR) process, and then machine learning algorithms can process the text on scanned documents to analyze the context. With the help of this information, the machine learning model classifies and indexes everything for future reference.

Machine learning-based document processing is also helpful for traditional banks that still rely on paper forms during the new client onboarding process. Whether it's a scan of an ID or an invoice, machine learning is a highly scalable and powerful tool for onboarding. Customers can open a bank account in just a few minutes, completing necessary checks in real-time. Such machine learning use cases help businesses build healthy and valuable relationships with their customers.

Text Processing

(Source: exadel.com)

Fraud Detection: -

Fraud in the fintech sector is becoming a common problem for many companies, regardless of the number of customers and size. Machine learning in finance can evaluate substantial data sets of simultaneous transactions in real-time. At the same time ML can minimize human input by learning from results and updating models. With the help of machine learning, financial organizations can label historical data as fraudulent or not fraudulent and continue to enhance their ability to detect possible potential fraud by learning from previous patterns of behavior. ML can help banks quickly identify user activity, verify it, and respond to cyber-attacks quickly and effectively.

A Typical Fraud Detection Process

Order

Machine learning model

Fraud risk estimate

Accept or reject

(Source: exadel.com)

In addition to rule-based fraud detection, machine learning allows for skimming through large amounts of data in real-time and minimizing human input. Additionally, it improves user experience by simplifying the identity verification measures.

Few differences between rule-based and ML-based fraud detection in the picture below: -

Rule-Based Fraud Detection

- Catching obvious fraudulent scenarios
- Requires a lot of manual work and human input to improve the system
- Requires time consuming verification process that harms user experience
- Long-term data processing

ML-Based Fraud Detection

- Finding hidden and implicit correlations in data
- Automatic detection of fraud scenarios
- Reduced number of verification steps, resulting in better user experience
- Real-time data processing

Customer Retention: -

Machine learning is a powerful tool that helps banks with customer support. Financial organizations turn to machine learning systems to fasten the support process and determine what a particular customer needs. What's more, ML-powered systems learn from their experience and improve over time, and are capable of processing increasingly more complex information.

Payments: -

The payment industry also benefits from incorporating machine learning in payment processes. The technology allows payment providers to reduce transaction costs and therefore attract more business. Among other

advantages of machine learning in payments is optimizing payment routing based on pricing, functionality, performance, and much more. By processing various data sources, machine learning systems can smoothly allocate traffic to the best performing combination of variables. This feature allows financial organizations to deliver the best results to merchants based on their specific objectives. Today, there are numerous machine learning applications for finance on the market, which serve as an excellent tool for companies to generate deep value by solving widespread problems. With the help of machine learning in payment processing, payment providers can identify whether a transaction should go ahead or first be routed to a two-step verification page.

(Source: exadel.com)

Chapter-3: Feasibility Study of Project

3.1 Feasibility of Project: -

Blockchain is not yet widespread in the banking industry but it is slowly getting there. There are many streamlining processes that financial institutions including banks need to keep in mind while adopting blockchain. For one, banks should have the required infrastructure for blockchain and ensure that each they follow the worldwide standards for this technology. It is only possible to implement blockchain all over the world when this happens. And there are significant advantages once blockchain becomes a global standard, it will lead to more transparent banking systems, faster processing of transactions, and reduced processing costs. All in all, the future of blockchain in banking seems very bright.

Applications of Blockchain and ML in Banking

- ***Person to Person Transactions***

Most people are familiar with person-to-person transactions as they are quite common. They involve a person paying another person from their bank account or credit card. There are many person-to-person apps available in different countries. Paytm in India is just one example.

However, a disadvantage of these apps is that they are only relevant in a particular country or geographical region and cannot be used to pay money to people in other countries. This problem can be resolved using blockchain as it has no geographical limitations. So crypto coins can be used for person-to-person transactions all over the world. The only important thing to keep in mind is exchange rates and that people may lose some money in this process.

- ***International Money Transfers***

Blockchain is being increasingly used for international money transfers by many banks. This is because international payments are much cheaper using blockchain as compared to traditional methods. How much cheap you ask? Well, overhead costs with blockchain are around 2-3% of the

total amount while these costs using traditional methods like Western Union, Swift, etc. can be as much as 5-20%. Another advantage of blockchain is that international payments do not require a third-party authorization, which makes it a much faster process than traditional money transfer methods.

- ***Online Identity Verification***

It is not possible to complete any financial transactions online without online verification and identification. And this is true for all the possible service providers any user might have in the financial and banking industry. However, blockchain can centralize the online identity verification process so that users only need to verify their identity once using blockchain, and then they can share this identity with whichever service provider they want. Users also have the option to choose their identity verification method such as user authentication, facial recognition, etc.

- ***Transaction Tracking***

Transaction tracking is an absolutely critical part of banking and blockchain is very helpful here as well. Financial companies and banks can use blockchain to create a centralized joint register of transactions that is extremely secure. This means there would be no data redundancies and chances of forging would also be reduced as all the transactions are available centrally. However, some banking professionals believe that blockchain would not be suitable for centralizing all types of transactions but useful for niche areas such as interbank transfers.

Chapter-4: Conclusion and Future scope for further development

The technologies of Blockchain and Machine Learning has gained salience in current time, here, we have put up an idea of integrating both of these technologies together for a future ready more secure, user friendly and sustainable Banking.

The idea is to make some changes in our existing banking working such as using the Machine Learning technology for more interactive, customer oriented and personalized banking which will add up to easy Identification and validation of the customer along with providing the extra layer of security by fraud detection. The centralized banking system can be swapped by the Decentralized Blockchain system which is very much secure and reliable along with that all the information related to a particular customer can be stored in a separate blockchain.

The presence of Hash values, encryption by using SHA256 algorithm, salting, nonce, mining etc. make the blockchain very much secure. Thus, combining the Machine Learning technologies can bring immense and drastic change in our Banking system and make it future ready and safe from any kind of hacking and data leakage and making it customer oriented with the help of Machine Learning.

References

- “*An efficient parallel machine learning-based blockchain framework*” by Korean scientists: Chun-Wei Tsai, Yi-Ping Chen, Tzu- Chieh Tang and Yu-Chen Luo.
 - “*Blockchain technology in supply chain management: insights from machine learning algorithms*” by Japanese scientists: Enna Hirata and Daisuke Watanabe with a Greek scientist Maria Lambrou.
 - “*Leveraging Blockchain for retraining deep learning architecture in patient-specific arrhythmia classification*” by American scientists: Amit Juneja and Michael Marefat.
 - “*Machine learning in/for blockchain: Future and challenges*” by Fang Chen, Hong Wan, Hua Cai, Guang Cheng.
 - “*P2TIF: A Blockchain and Deep Learning Framework for Privacy-Preserved Threat Intelligence in Industrial IoT*” by Indian Scientists: Prabhat Kumar, Randhir Kumar, Govind P. Gupta, Rakesh Tripathi, Gautam Srivastava.
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